

CREATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ASTRONOMY EDUCATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *The article presents a study of the relevance of the application of creative methods of teaching astronomy in secondary education of Uzbekistan, especially in the context of the modern development of science and technology. Based on theoretical and practical aspects, the article discusses the importance of using the principles of teaching astronomy in this age group. During the study, methods for creative teaching of astronomy were developed and described, aimed at shaping students' ideas about the modern scientific astronomical picture of the world.*

The article analyzes the results of pedagogical experiments, which proved that creative teaching of astronomy significantly increases students' interest in science and contributes to the development of their creative thinking and potential. Specific examples of methods and tools that can be used to create an attractive and effective learning environment are considered. The main principles of creative teaching of astronomy in secondary education are games, experiments, communication, creativity, and the use of various visualization tools. These methods and principles help students to better understand theory and scientific facts and enable them to participate in activities.

Thus, this article can become the basis for the development of new methods and approaches to teaching astronomy in secondary education, as well as for improving the effectiveness of existing methods. It can also be an important contribution to developing the scientific and creative potential of students and ensuring their successful adaptation to the modern world of science and technology.

Keywords: *astronomy, secondary education, creativity, development.*

Introduction

The current state of society has set the task of restructuring the general education for the lifelong education system. This task involves the development of students' creative potential, which should lead to the modernization of the existing traditional education system.

Scientists have established that a student with a high creative potential differs from others in that: - has a creative and intellectual initiative, an active life position; - able to generate new original ideas in solving problematic issues; - can go beyond patterns and think creatively, resolve conflicts that have arisen; - is able to represent ideas from his/her mind and also construct the future result of his activity; - a creative student has an original way out of a problematic situation that has arisen in the educational process; - a creative one is characterized by a constant research need, which allows him/her to be in a state of constant search for the previously unknown (Runco and Jaeger, 2012).

Research of scientists allowed us to identify creative qualities as an integral characteristic of a person, which include imagination, a sense of novelty, originality of thinking, intuition, fantasy, inventing, fine art, logical thinking, etc. (Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009).

To develop the creative potential of students, the development of a special technology is required, which is the subject of this article.

The model of the process of developing the creative potential of students that we propose consists of three stages, which are applied both in traditional and innovative forms of education. However, with an innovative form of teaching, the greatest performance is achieved (Cropley, 2010):

the motivational-indicative stage of the model helps students to formulate the learning task themselves by performing creative tasks and orients them towards learning new material;

the operational-executive stage allows students to program the process of cognition through the division of the educational task into private tasks and the solution of problematic issues by organizing individual or group work;

the reflective-evaluative stage brings students to independent conclusions, assessment and self-assessment of knowledge; Each lesson ends with a creative homework assignment.

The proposed model for the development of the creative potential of students fits well with extracurricular activities, the main components of which are games and research work of the participants.

The proposed technology for developing the creative potential of students radically changes the entire course of the educational process. The model allows to organize lessons in a completely different way - seminars that activate even the most passive students. In our case, such learning technologies as “technology of technical creativity”, “heuristic immersion in the subject”, “self-reasoning on the problem”, “historical alchemy”, “French workshops”, “model of binary oppositions”, “crossing destinies”, etc. help to revitalize the learning process.

It should be noted that there are empirical prerequisites for the development of the creative potential of students.

Pedagogical systems have evolved over time, with notable figures such as Comenius (2012) and Pestalozzi (2012) contributing to early education. Later, educational approaches were developed and improved upon by psychologists and educators such as Piaget & Inhelder (1972), Bruner (1976) and Montessori (2007). Today, the search for new forms of education that can effectively assimilate complex information without mental strain or harm to health continues, with a need for creative collaboration between philosophers, psychologists, didacticists, methodologists, and practicing teachers.

To achieve the goal of developing the creative potential of students and testing the effectiveness of this teaching technology, it was necessary to organize experimental training. The results of the control experiment showed the effectiveness of this teaching technology for the development of the creative potential of students.

The conducted research is aimed at developing the creative potential of students of a secondary school, based on the implementation of the proposed teaching technology.

During the study, the works of different scientists on the topic of the article were analyzed and the essence of the concepts of "creativity" and "creative potential" was revealed. At the same time, we consider creative potential to be a broader concept than creativity, supplementing its essence with such criteria as “sensitivity to the problem”, “ability to analyze and synthesize, to create the missing details of the object under study”, “divergence of thinking”.

The didactic requirements for the creative teaching of astronomy in a holistic teaching system are determined. These are the requirements: 1) compliance with the mandatory minimum

content of astronomical education, 2) interactivity of models, 3) feedback, 4) providing conditions for the formation of research skills, 5) unity of teaching and controlling functions, 6) diversity of types and differentiation of tasks, 7) compliance opportunities for students and the creation of conditions for individual growth.

In the course of the study, a model for the development of the creative potential of students in astronomy was proposed, consisting of the goal, principles, content of the teaching technology. The organization of experimental training contributed to the successful implementation of this technology.

On the basis of the experiment, the relevance of the problem of applying a creative approach to teaching astronomy in the education system is substantiated. Methods for teaching astronomy with a creative approach have been developed for secondary school education. Based on the study of Beghetto & Kaufman (2010) a structure of the complex of creative tools in astronomy is proposed, which ensures not only the achievement of high results in teaching students, but also the development of their personal growth.

It is creativity that will seriously affect the further development of society. As we know, teaching how to learn and apply the knowledge gained is more important than simply appropriating a specific set of knowledge. It should be noted that the development of creative potential is one of the most important sources and indicators of the prosperity of our society (Sternberg, 2003). Based on the above tasks, it should be noted that instilling information from early childhood will give good results, including what interests us today, the instillation of elements of astronomical ideas.

According to Hayes (2006) *secondary education* is aimed at developing the foundations of literacy, knowledge and skills necessary for obtaining a general secondary education. Based on the fact that the goal of general secondary education is to equip students with a systematic knowledge of the fundamentals of science, the skills and abilities necessary for activities in various areas of the economy, culture and life, as well as for receiving special education, it is of great importance in preparing for further education (Grigg, 2016). That is why it is necessary to consider more deeply the issues of introducing elements of astronomical concepts from the very first stages in school education.

It should be noted that physics lessons significantly benefit from the use of astronomical material. The physics curricula from the 6th grade onwards include several questions related to pure astronomy. When discussing these topics, it is easy to integrate them with physics questions, which often helps students understand physics concepts more effectively, as astronomical issues are often presented in a more visual and engaging manner.

When studying the initial topics in the 6th to 7th grades, such as "What Does Physics Study," it is beneficial to consider questions from astronomy: the objects studied in physics—including those in near-Earth space and the macrocosm. In discussions about basic physical quantities, examples from astronomy are provided.

For example, regarding "length," examples include the radius of the Earth, the diameter of the Sun, the diameter of the Solar System, the distance to the nearest star to the Solar System, and the diameter of the observable universe. An example of how the radius of the Earth is measured is included; for "mass," the masses of the Earth, Sun, Milky Way galaxy, and systems of galaxies are discussed; for "time," the age of the Earth, the age of the universe, and the time it takes for light to travel from the Sun to the Earth are covered, etc.

In the topic "Mechanical Motion," the reasons for the change of day and night, the change of seasons, and the trajectories of the planets in the Solar System and comets are examined; examples of the speeds of celestial bodies are provided.

When discussing "Relative Motion," an example is considered: How far have we traveled while sitting in class during a 40-minute lesson relative to the center of our galaxy? The rotation speed of the Earth around its axis, the orbital speed of the Earth, and the speed of the Solar System relative to the center of the galaxy are taken into account. The trajectory of this movement is also illustrated. This topic also includes values of cosmic speeds.

In the topic "Density," examples of the highest and lowest densities in the material world are given, which also include objects from the Solar System, such as the density of neutron stars.

When studying the topic "Forces," the significance of gravity on different planets in the Solar System is examined and compared to its value on Earth. Each student has a table of gravitational acceleration values for the planets in the Solar System, allowing them to calculate the weight of a physics textbook on different planets and to explain the presence or absence of an atmosphere on those planets. It is worth noting that elements of astronomy have been studied and continue to be studied within the framework of the school physics curriculum, as physical laws are the foundation of all natural science subjects.

Additionally, astrophysical material is included in the 9th-grade physics curriculum. The section "Structure and Evolution of the Universe" contains the following elements: the composition, structure, and origin of the Solar System; planets and small bodies of the Solar System; the structure, radiation, and evolution of the Sun, stars, and the universe. The learning objectives for this section include:

- Understanding the composition, structure, origin, and age of the Solar System;
- The ability to apply physical laws to explain the motion of the planets in the Solar System;
- Knowing that the significant parameters distinguishing stars from planets are their masses and energy sources;

- Comparing the physical and orbital parameters of terrestrial planets with those of giant planets and identifying their similarities and differences;

- Explaining the essence of the Doppler effect;

- Formulating and explaining the essence of Hubble's law, and knowing that this law provided experimental confirmation of the model of a non-stationary universe proposed by Friedman.

Moreover, elements of astronomy are present in the following topics:

- Physical Nature of Celestial Bodies in the Solar System (7th grade)

- Gravity on Other Planets (7th grade)

- The Earth's Magnetic Field (8th grade)

- Apparent Motion of Celestial Bodies (8th grade)

- Geocentric and Heliocentric Models of the Universe (9th grade)

- The Law of Universal Gravitation (9th grade)

- Energy Sources of the Sun and Stars (9th grade)

As demonstrations while studying elements of astronomy in the physics curriculum for grades 7-9, it is acceptable to widely use tables, models, presentations, and video materials. There are several video lessons explaining elements of astronomy that can be used in physics classes, making lessons more visual and interesting. During the research, a large number of video lessons

were reviewed and analyzed. Among them, the following lessons stand out: "The Phenomenon of Gravity. The Force of Gravity"; "The Earth's Magnetic Field"; "The Apparent Motion of Celestial Bodies"; "The Law of Universal Gravitation"; "The Motion of Planets and Artificial Satellites"; "The Structure of the Solar System"; "The Earth-Moon System"; "General Information About the Sun"; "Energy Sources and Internal Structure of the Sun"; "The Physical Nature of Stars".

Research questions

1. Do teachers use new creative methods in the lessons?
2. Is it possible to substantiate the relevance of the problem of applying a creative approach in teaching astronomy on the basis of an experiment?
3. Does the use of creative methods contribute to the achievement of a higher level in teaching astronomical concepts to school students?
4. What structure of the complex of creative methods in astronomy ensures not only the achievement of high results in teaching students, but also the development of their personal growth?
5. How effective is the proposed method for applying the developed complex? Is it possible to experimentally test and show the impact of the use of these tools on the formation of interest in science, the development of cognitive independence of students and the improvement of the knowledge in astronomy?

Method

There are several new teaching methods in creative, playful and interactive forms, that can be used in secondary schools. Next, we present creative technologies, ways of conveying astronomical concepts in creative, playful and interactive forms of teaching, which we have applied in school institutions.

Table 1. Creative teaching of astronomical phenomena to students in secondary education

№	Name of creative methods and learning technologies	Brief Description
1.	Reflection method	The reflection method involves creating the necessary conditions for students to independently comprehend the material and develop their ability to adopt an active research position towards the studied content. The educational process occurs through the completion of assignments by students, with systematic checks of their results, during which errors, difficulties, and the most successful solutions are noted.
2.	"Leader-Follower" method	According to this method, one student (or group) joins a more experienced student (or group) to master unfamiliar skills and competencies. The advantages of this method lie in its simplicity, the quicker adaptation of students to new activities, and the enhancement of communication skills.
3.	Rotation method	The rotation method involves assigning different roles to students during a lesson or session, allowing them to gain diverse experiences. The benefits of this method include its positive

		impact on student motivation, helping to overcome the negative effects of routine activities, and expanding horizons and social circles.
4.	Analysis of "backlogs"	The backlog analysis method consists of simulating situations that frequently arise in real life and involve a significant amount of work, as well as developing the most effective ways to solve problems caused by such situations. This method is characterized by high student motivation, their active participation in problem-solving processes, and an emphasis on developing analytical skills and systematic thinking.
5.	Case technology	Case technology combines role-playing, project methods, and situational analysis. In case technology, a real situation is analyzed, the description of which highlights a specific set of knowledge that must be mastered to resolve the issue. In active situational learning, participants are presented with facts related to a situation at a given moment in time. Students' task is to make rational decisions while engaging in collective discussions of possible solutions.
6.	Problem-based learning technology	The problem-based learning technology involves organizing independent search activities for students under the guidance of a teacher to solve educational problems. During this process, students form new knowledge, skills, and competencies, as well as develop abilities such as cognitive activity, curiosity, erudition, creative thinking, and other personally significant qualities. Problematic assignments can include educational tasks, questions, practical assignments, etc. Generally, the technology of problem-based learning consists of presenting students with a problem, which they investigate, either with the teacher's direct involvement or independently, to explore paths and methods for its solution.
7.	Facts method	The facts method is a means of observation and fact collection.
8.	Training	Training is a teaching method that emphasizes the practical aspect of the educational process, while the theoretical component is of secondary importance.

Organization of the pedagogical experiment and its conditions

The purpose of the experimental study was to establish the effectiveness of the introduction of methods for creative teaching of astronomy, the possibility of enhancing cognitive independence and creativity, improving the quality of assimilation of students' knowledge based on creative teaching of astronomy. The given results of psychological-pedagogical and methodical literature served as the basis for putting forward the idea of the study.

The main objectives of the pedagogical experiment were:

Finding out the need to create and apply methods of creative teaching of astronomy in the secondary education.

Finding out the need to create modern guidelines for the use of creative teaching methods.

Checking the possibility of using creative teaching methods, as well as checking the assumption about the effectiveness of the methodology for the integrated application in teaching astronomy, educational and developmental tasks of secondary school, and the development of students' creative, cognition.

Implementation of guidelines on the use of creative methods in astronomy and determination of the impact of the integrated use of creative methods on increasing the cognitive independence of students.

Pedagogical experiments were carried out among:

School students and teachers of secondary school №10 of the Tashkent region (Uzbekistan) - Grade 8 "A", Grade 8 "B" (60 students). The experiments were carried out from September 2021 to March 2022 in three stages: *1 - ascertaining, 2 - main search and 3 - final training experiment.*

Ascertaining stage

Ascertaining experiment at the first stage revealed the main problems of teaching astronomy. The discrepancy between the existing methods and modern didactic requirements was stated. From conversations with educators and teachers, it was revealed that new methods of teaching astronomy with a creative approach are needed. At the second stage of the ascertaining experiment, a teaching model was created. The ascertaining experiment at this stage consisted in identifying the main problems of the effectiveness of teaching astronomy using creative methods:

explaining astronomical phenomena that can arouse the interest of secondary school students in astronomical concepts;

organizing the preparation of appropriate training for teachers.

At the same stage, the analysis of the state of modern astronomical education began on the basis of conversations with "teachers and students", their questioning and the study of pedagogical experience.

Search stage

In order to test and identify the effectiveness of creative methods and their application in teaching astronomy, it was necessary to organize and conduct an appropriate pedagogical experiment. The purpose of this ongoing experiment was to study the factor on the object of research. Cognitive interest and, as a result, the development of cognitive independence of students is an important reason for improvement and at the same time an indicator of the effectiveness and efficiency of the learning process. Data on the levels of cognitive independence of students were used as the output variable. The achievement by students of three levels of cognitive independence was considered: reproductive, partially exploratory and research, psychological and didactic aspects of achieving levels of cognitive independence were summarized.

Training stage

The training experiment consisted of conducting lessons using creative methods in astronomy in the secondary education, called experimental ones. The comparison was made with classes where teaching was conducted without the use of creative teaching methods. During the experiment, the requirement of representativeness was taken into account in the selection of experimental and control classes in order to avoid the unreliability of the results of the pedagogical experiment. Since the improvement in the quality of classes and the creative development of students occurs not only from the use of new creative methods and teaching methods, but also from a significant number of other factors, the relationship should not be a functional dependence, but a correlation relationship.

During the experimental work, various research methods were used: observation of students, analysis of diagnostic tests, analysis of the creative growth of students, their degree of participation in the classroom.

In our case of selective observation, the parameters of the entire set of objects to be examined are unknown. They can only be judged hypothetically. To assess these parameters in pedagogy, the null hypothesis is used, which proceeds from the assumption that the observed changes in properties do not depend on the action of an organized parameter, but are determined by secondary, unregulated random causes in the educational process.

Hypothesis. As a null hypothesis H_0 , we put forward the assumption that the development of cognitive independence did not increase after the experiment, there was no correction of knowledge, skills and abilities. Let us form the opposite hypothesis H_1 : the application of creative methods of teaching astronomy in secondary education contributes to the development of creative potentials. In the course of hypothesis testing, we will decide which of the statements is true in the light of empirical evidence. Let us take the probability of erroneous rejection of the hypothesis - the level of significance with the usual value of $p = 0,05$. We extract the sample and for the obtained empirical data we determine the statistical criterion and determine the probability of which of their hypotheses is correct.

Correlation coefficient, plotting will be obtained using the STATISTICA system. The STATISTICA system is an integrated system for statistical analysis and data processing. Data in STATISTICA is entered in the form of a table, the correlation coefficient r is calculated automatically.

In the course of testing the hypothesis, a comparison was made of the knowledge and skills of all the participants in the experiment in completing the district diagnostic test in astronomy. During the experiment, the requirement of representativeness was taken into account in the selection of experimental and control classes in order to avoid unreliability of the experimental results.

The experimental group, at the first stage of the experiment, was grade 8 “A” of secondary school №10 was chosen as an experimental class among secondary classes. Grade 8 “B” class was chosen as a control class. 60 number of students of a secondary school and teachers also took part in the expert assessment of the work of students according to the proposed model using creative methods and with a creative approach.

Results

Analysis of the survey of secondary school teachers

Table 2. Answers of secondary school teachers to question №1

Question №1. What modern teaching methods do you use in astronomy lessons?		
Answer options	teachers' answers before the experiment (%)	teachers' answers after experiment (%)
Cooperation pedagogy	57	40
Gaming technologies	17	16
Problem based learning	42	36
Project method	23	51
Study	15	14
Level differentiation	32	31

Group technologies	27	25
Individualization of learning	18	14
Programmed learning	7	3
Creative teaching methods	19	58

Figure 1. Use of modern teaching methods in secondary schools

From the analysis of the results of answers to this part of the questions, it can be seen that the number of teachers who use creative teaching methods in the classroom has increased dramatically (from 19% to 58%).

Table 3. Answers of secondary school teachers to question №2

Question №2. How often do you use the following types of lessons?						
Type of lesson	Before the experiment			After the experiment		
	never	rarely	often	never	rarely	often
Lecture	1	16.5	60	1	17	57
Story lesson	2	11	55	2	10	54
Video lesson	8	29	40	5	23	41
Seminar	3.6	30	36	3	22	33
Research lesson	17	28	3	18	27	3
Conference	11	32.8	6	10	35	5
Creative lesson	37.6	8.2	6	16	18	67

Analyzing the answers of teachers to this question of the questionnaire, it can be concluded that the number of teachers choosing a creative type of lesson has increased. It is worth noting that the teachers emphasized that with the use of creative methods, the quality of the lesson has changed significantly, and the interest and discipline of the students have been improved.

Table 4. Answers of secondary school teachers to question №3

Question №3. Do you consider yourself ready for active work using creative methods in explaining astronomical concepts?				
Members	Teacher responses before the experiment		Teacher responses after the experiment	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Secondary school teachers	47%	53%	75%	25%

The analysis of teachers' answers to these questions prompted the development of creative lessons, cooperation with teachers and heated discussions on the further use of such methods step by step, interest is increased in the integrity and continuity of teaching astronomy, as well as its further results.

The developed creative methods for teaching astronomical phenomena and astronomy in general, in secondary schools, were applied in the classroom, tested for effectiveness, amendments were made, recommendations and ideas of secondary school teachers were studied.

Search experiment results

Table 5. Answers of secondary school teachers to question №4

Question №4. Are you interested in the organization of creative methods in astronomy lessons in the system of continuous education?				
Members	Teacher responses before the experiment		Teacher responses after the experiment	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
Secondary school teachers	53%	47%	75%	25%

The achievement by students of three levels of cognitive independence was considered: reproductive, partially exploratory and research, psychological and didactic aspects of achieving levels of cognitive independence are summarized in the table.

Table 6. Psychological and didactic aspects of the formation of cognitive independence through the methods of educational activity

Ability Development	Level characteristic	Achieved level of development of cognitive independence
Development of copying ability	It is characterized by the student's desire to understand, remember and reproduce knowledge, to master the way of its application according to the model. The criterion for this level of activity is the desire of students to understand the phenomenon under study.	Reproductive
Reproducing creative activity	It is characterized by the student's desire to reveal the meaning of the content being studied, to penetrate into the essence of the phenomenon, to know the connection between phenomena and processes, to master the ways of applying knowledge in changed conditions.	Partial search
Development of the ability of constructive and creative activity	It is characterized not only by interest and desire to penetrate deeply into the essence of phenomena and their relationships, but also to find a new way.	Research

In accordance with the main ideas of the study, we set tasks, the solution of which was to confirm the correctness of the proposed hypothesis. During the search stage, tests were carried out. They were attended by groups of participants from school institutions.

Thus, after the results of the test questions, it finally confirmed the assumption that the use of creative methods in teaching contributes to the achievement of a higher level of development of cognitive independence.

During the exploratory phase of the experiment, the didactic tasks of astronomy teaching tools, the search for various forms and methodological teaching methods, the search for models of creative lessons in astronomy, the selection and specification of tasks for independent search and research activities using creative methods were identified. Participants noted that one of the benefits of using a variety of creative tools is that participants can organize their work in an interesting creative format.

An important part of the search stage of the experiment was the analysis of the practical application of creative lesson development, the search for a structure for advanced training of astronomy teachers, which contributes to the introduction of new creative technologies in teaching astronomy.

NUMERIC VALUES	1 EXP1	2 CONT2	3 VAR3	4 VAR4	5 VAR5
зад1	89,000	37,000			
зад2	89,000	38,000			
зад3	98,000	53,000			
зад4	99,000	53,000			
зад5	89,000	55,000			
зад6	87,000	52,000			
зад7	77,000	52,000			
зад8	77,000	52,000			
зад9	77,000	46,000			
зад10	77,000	54,000			
зад11	91,000	52,000			
зад12	92,000	50,000			
зад13	79,000	45,000			
зад14	79,000	45,000			
зад15	99,000	28,000			
зад16	99,000	28,000			

Figure 2. Data entry into the integrated system of statistical analysis STATISTICA

For these schools, a chart of the results of the average grades for the two groups was constructed. On the results diagram, built in three dimensions, two areas of correlation were clearly distinguished. The same result can be seen in the more well-known two-dimensional diagrams.

Figure 3. Volumetric diagram of the test results

The correlation coefficient $r = -0,37$, which for $p < 0,05$ indicates that there is a moderate relationship. A more visual representation of the correlation can be obtained by analyzing the graphs of the dependences of the control and experimental groups relative to each other.

Figure 4. Correlation calculation

Figure 5. Graphical representation of the dependences of the experimental and control groups with correlation calculation

Thus, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Consequently, the distribution of the results of performing diagnostic test after the application of creative teaching methods in the system of continuous education is statistically significant. The analysis of this pedagogical experiment confirms our hypothesis with a certainty of at least 95% that the use of creative teaching methods improves the quality of knowledge, this is not due to random factors, but has a natural character.

Results of the training experiment

Comparison of the results of the element-by-element analysis of the tests of the experimental and the averaged results of the control classes leads to the following conclusions: the average percentage of completing tasks in terms of complexity is the same for the experimental and control classes, that is, the general trends in completing tasks are the same, but the level of completion of all tasks in the experimental class is higher. Further, we can see this in the following figures, which show the results of the tasks, before and after the experiment, among the experimental and control groups.

Figure 6. The average assessment of the performance of tasks in the experimental and control classes of school №10

According to the results of the experiment, it can be seen that the quality of knowledge and the level of assimilation are higher in the experimental grade 8 "A", and the average score for completing tasks is 4.7 points, on a 5-point scale. While the average score for completing tasks in the control grade 8 "B" is 4 points.

Discussion

These studies are reduced to the following provisions:

The number of teachers using creative methods in the classroom has increased, teachers have begun to apply new creative methods constantly.

The complex application of creative techniques contributes to the achievement of a higher level of personal development.

Analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment as a whole confirms the hypothesis with at least 95% confidence that there is a relationship between the use of creative methods and improving the quality of knowledge, achieving a research level of cognitive independence.

On the basis of the experiment, the relevance of the problem of applying a creative approach in teaching astronomy is substantiated.

Such a structure of the complex of creative means in astronomy is proposed, which ensures not only the achievement of high results in teaching students, but also the development of their personal growth.

The effectiveness of the methodology for using the developed set of tools was experimentally tested and the impact of using these tools on the formation of interest in science, the development of students' cognitive independence and the improvement of the quality of knowledge in astronomy was shown.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study presented in this article highlights the importance of using creative methods of teaching astronomy in secondary education in Uzbekistan. The article discusses the theoretical and practical aspects of creative teaching of astronomy and presents various methods and principles that can be used to make learning more effective and enjoyable for students. The results of pedagogical experiments conducted as part of the study demonstrate that creative teaching of astronomy can significantly increase students' interest in science and contribute to the development of their creative thinking and potential. This study has important implications for the

development of new and improved methods of teaching astronomy in secondary education, and for promoting the scientific and creative potential of students in Uzbekistan.

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